

DETERMINING INVALIDITY OF TREATIES IN INTERNATIONAL LAW DOCTRINE

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Abstract: The validity of a treaty is a paramount aspect that determines the legally binding nature of an international instrument. A treaty is considered valid if it meets the necessary requirements of international law, such as the voluntary consent of the parties involved, the capacity of the parties to enter into a treaty, and the observance of the principles of international law. The validity of a treaty is essential in ensuring that the parties involved adhere to the terms of the treaty and that the treaty is enforceable and recognized by the international community. Thus, the validity of a treaty is a critical factor in establishing its legal authority and binding power.

Keywords: treaties, international law, international treaties law, validity, legally binding, invalidity, error, fraud, coercion, jus cogens.

Treaties are recognized as legally binding agreements that serve as fundamental tools for governing international relations. They are established in accordance with international law doctrine and can be formed between sovereign states, states and international organisations, or among international organisations. Treaties address a wide range of subjects, including trade, environmental protection, human rights, and security, and play a crucial role in shaping the global legal framework [1; p. 177].

Since, treaties occupy a very eminent position in international law, first of all, a brief description of the concept of the “treaty” for the full imagination of the treaty-making process should be analyzed. Furthermore, the legal character of significant

factors affecting the legality and authentication of an international instrument, such as “validity” and “the consent to be bound by a treaty” must be examined.

While discussing the matter of the validity of treaties, including the factors affecting the validity, along with methods of expressing the consent to be bound by a treaty should be analyzed complexly.

Article 42, paragraph 1 of the VCLT states that the validity of a treaty or a state’s consent to be bound by a treaty can only be challenged following the Convention. In other words, article 42 of the VCLT stipulates that a treaty can only be terminated or ended by any other means through the application of the provisions of the Convention or the respective treaty provisions.

As it’s known, states create sources of international law, which are only valid as a system of rules with their duly and fully expressed consent. In this regard, to have a clearer understanding of these concepts, the validity of treaties is analyzed in the present paragraph, and a separate paragraph in the present research is dedicated to the general principles of the expression of the consent to be bound by a treaty. Therefore, the research of the validity of an international instrument is primarily conducted by analysis through the prism of VCLT and Convention from 1986.

For instance, Von der Decken specifies that Article 42 contains the rule of the exhaustive application of the VCLT and of the respective treaty provisions in terms of ceasing the operation of a treaty. In fact, this provision is governed by the principle of legality as Article 42 is not a substantive rule with normative quality, but rather a legislative provision that determines how to use the substantive rules of the VCLT and the respective treaty. Certain authors explain that Article 42 of the VCLT assumes that a treaty is valid and ongoing by default. Therefore, if a participant in a treaty claims that it is invalid, terminated, or suspended, they must provide evidence to support their claim [2; p.791-792].

While discussing the concept of the validity of international instruments, A.N. Talalayev, defines the validity of an international treaty as its international

legal completeness, first of all, legality, under which the treaty is binding for its implementation by counterparties and respected by all other subjects of international law [3; p.148].

It is important to analyze certain elements that are necessary for the validity of an international instrument. These elements include the power to conclude an international treaty, the consent of all parties involved, and requirements for registration and publication of the treaty. By examining these components, we can better understand the institution of the validity of an international instrument.

For instance, the power to conclude an international treaty is given to states (article 6 of VCLT) and international organizations (article 6 of the Convention from 1986). Moreover, the power to conclude an international treaty more relevantly belongs to the institute of “full powers”, which is analyzed further in the present research.

Furthermore, the other element mentioned above – consent of the parties, which is an eminent factor in treaty-making capacity, specified in Articles 11 through 17 of VCLT, is a separate independent institute, directly affecting the validity of any international instrument.

In addition, based on paragraph 1 of Article 42 of the VCLT could be emphasized that the concept of “validity” and the idea of “the consent to be bound by a treaty” are highly relevant to and affecting each other, but at the same time, independent and separate institutions of international law of treaties.

The final element in the scope of our analysis is the requirements for registration and publication of a treaty. Article 80 of the VCLT is dedicated to the registration and publication of international instruments, which stipulates that international instruments are sent to the depositary for registration and publication (as the case may be) after they have entered into force.

Thereby, firstly, if an international instrument has already entered into force, it could be stipulated that the treaty on its own is already valid. Secondly, the

publication of an international instrument may in some cases be not considered by its provisions. Therefore, requirements for registration and publication of a treaty could be assumed as a separate institution of international law theory, affecting the validity of a treaty in particular cases.

The concept of validity is influenced by and related to the binding force of treaties. To this extent, some authors claim that understanding the validity of an international instrument does not necessarily reflect the mandatory force of such an instrument, but in contrast, validity usually presupposes that it is applicable in a particular society and should be accepted as such by its members.

Furthermore, if previously there may have been a high degree of correspondence between the concepts of “legally valid” and “legally binding”, now it is plausible to assume that documents that are not legally binding should nevertheless be checked for validity [4; p. 83-118].

Therefore, the bindingness of a treaty may be influenced by validity (invalidity) thoughts, as well as other considerations. Hence, a treaty may never enter into force and consequently, it does not become legally binding, but not owing to a failure based on validity. On the contrary, an instrument may be terminated and cease to be valid and binding, still, its binding nature does not discontinue by the breach of its validity [5; p. 282].

Taking into account the above opinions on the concept of “legally binding” and “legally validness” of international treaties, in the present research we derive from the consideration that if an international instrument is legally valid there must have been followed to achieve some purposes to fulfill before the treaty was concluded. Thus, these assigned tasks and goals are fulfilled via the implementation of some kind of norms, provisions, or recommendations. These norms or provisions should carry binding power to establish, amend, or abolish legal facts. The statement that an international instrument may be valid but at the same time not legally binding could be suitable only when an international instrument itself from the beginning

does not carry binding character. For instance, declarations, memorandums of understanding or intent in most cases carry recommending character or establish the basis of understanding or intent, which does not contain legally binding provisions.

Therefore, while analyzing the relationship between the concepts of “legally binding” and “legally valid” in terms of international treaties, in the framework of the present research, the bottom line is that *if an international instrument is legally valid then it is legally binding unless the instrument itself is specifically established with the purpose of not carrying any legally binding nature.*

The other point to be examined in our complex analysis in the present research, as mentioned above, is factors affecting the validity of an international instrument. In this regard, basic factors affecting the validity of treaties could be categorized as follows: (a) lacking the competence (capacity) to conclude treaties, (b) concluded under specific restrictions on authority to express the consent of a state, (c) containing an error, (d) concluded by fraud, (e) concluded by corruption of a representative of a state, (f) concluded under the coercion of a state representative, (g) concluded under the coercion of a state by the threat or use of force, (h) conflicting with a peremptory norm of general international law (“*jus cogens*”).

However, some authors in addition to the abovementioned factors, underline conflicting treaty provisions as a nowadays vanishing basis for the invalidity of treaties [6; p. 208-232].

Nevertheless, in the present research, the concept of the conflict of treaties is considered more related to the hierarchy of treaties, including the implementation of successive treaties dealing with the same subject matter.

The institution of the validity of a treaty could be affected by many factors, including (but not least) the power to conclude an international treaty, the consent of the participants, and requirements for registration and publication of a treaty, but the bottom line is these aspects are not components constituting the institute of validity, they are separate concepts of international law doctrine.

Considering the above mentioned, the most significant component validity basis on is the legality or legal authentication in full and complete form. The concept of complete legal authentication covers the full legal rightness and correct accomplishment and completeness of all necessary procedures, including rightful expression of the consent to be bound by a treaty from its participants, appropriately provided full powers, proper registration and publication, and other legal formalities, indicated in the treaty itself for its entry into force. Other formalities could be fulfilling all necessary interstate procedures for the treaty's entry into force etc.

Furthermore, should be noted that Section 2 of the VCLT is dedicated to determining the invalidity of treaties. Particularly, Articles 46 to 53 cover various aspects of invalidity.

In the present study, we derive from the point that invalidity may be separated into relative and absolute invalidity.

The concept of relative invalidity acknowledges that a treaty may be voidable, allowing the aggrieved state to establish its invalidity or choose to recognize its validity despite the presence of contentious elements. The basis for relative invalidity of international instruments according to VCLT are as follows: provisions of internal law regarding competence to conclude treaties (Article 46), specific restrictions on authority to express the consent of a State (Article 47), error (Article 48), fraud (Article 49) and corruption of a representative of a State (Article 50).

The term "absolute invalidity" signifies the complete annulment of a treaty from its inception, resulting in its nullity. Circumstances leading to absolute invalidity include coercion of a representative of the state or international organization; coercion of a state or international organization by means of the threat or use of force; a treaty that is inconsistent with a peremptory norms of general international law.

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